

Karadeniz Technical University

Department of English Language and Literature

**The Power of Nature and the Supernatural Powers in
William Shakespeare's "Macbeth"**

Burak DEMİR

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Abstract

This study examines the power of nature and the supernatural powers in Macbeth, the last and the shortest of Shakespeare's great tragedies, and their influence on the course of events in the play. Macbeth is the one of Shakespeare plays that supernatural figures and elements take place at most. The mainstays of the play are developing events as a result of the prophecies of the witches, supernatural powers' triggering human greed and as a result of this, deterioration, distortion and disorder occurring on the universal order. In this study, in which cases the harmony and balance of nature is impaired, what happens as a result of this deterioration and the perspectives of the people of Shakespeare's era about the witches were examined with comments by famous critics.

Keywords: nature, supernatural powers, Shakespeare, Macbeth

I. INTRODUCTION

I.I. SUMMARY

While returning a successful military campaign, two Scottish commanders Macbeth and Banquo came across with three witches and witches say that Macbeth will first entitle with Thane of Cawdor, then become the King and Banquo's descendants would continue the future of the kingdom. Thus, the statements of the witches come true and the messenger says that Macbeth will be rewarded as Thane of Cawdor by Duncan, the King of Scotland.

Lady Macbeth who heard about the witches encourages her husband Macbeth who began to dream about being a king to kill the King when he comes to their castle to visit. Macbeth kills Duncan. When the news about King's death is whispering, Macbeth executes the King's servants in order to cover up his crime. Duncan's sons Malcolm and Donalbain escape from Scotland, and Macbeth becomes king. Then he agrees with some assassins to kill Banquo and his son Fleance, however, Fleance manages to escape.

At a banquet given by Macbeth, the Banquo's ghost appears to Macbeth. He goes to the witches to consult and ask their advice; the witches tell him to beware Macduff, no man born of woman can harm him, he will never be defeated until Birnam Wood marches to fight him at Dunsinane Hill, and they reiterate that Banquo's descendants will be the king.

Meanwhile, Macduff who went to England with Malcolm to gather an army to kill Macbeth learns that his wife and children killed by Macbeth's command. Macbeth sets his army to meet the army of besiegers, and then he receives the news of Lady Macbeth's suicide. Macduff's army processes by hiding with the tree branches from Birnam forest and Macduff kills Macbeth. Malcolm is crowned as the King of Scotland.

I.II. THEORY

Not only in terms of subject matter, but also in terms of materials forming these matters, Shakespeare's plays have considerably wide varieties. It is frequently seen that in some parts of his plays, characters accompanied by gins, fairies and ghosts and in many times, the nature participate in the play like a character. People's world is supplemented in this manner and a relationship between the macro cosmos and micro cosmos is connected by these supernatural elements. In dramaturgic aspects, the functions of these powers which are organically connected with the play regain an understanding with the idea of universal harmony that we find traces in Shakespeare's many plays.

Starting point of the plays, also called "protasis" by Aristotle in *Poetics* (Crivelli 1), is a point where the balance and harmony are broken and the moral values became upside-down. This disorder reaches a chaos in some plays. The results of this deterioration not only affect small areas, but also influence larger areas. In other words, in Shakespeare, the corruptive action confronts to reader as a threat to the stability of the universe. The order disruptors are punished in a way at the end of the play, thereby, a sort of literary justice is provided. However, the justice of Shakespeare never contains such a closed-end harmony which will never fail again. The knots indicating that someone will re-disrupt the harmony are already knitted. Perhaps, the re-established temporary harmony is a renewal of the faith in life.

On the other hand, in restoring or re-establishing the order, the powers other than human beings will also play an important role. However, of course, the leading role is always the Nature.

II. DISCUSSION

II.I. THE PROCESS OF WRITING OF MACBETH AND THE CRITICISMS

Macbeth is the last and shortest of Shakespeare's four great tragedies. It is considered that the play was written and staged in 1606. The only extant text of Macbeth is a partially damaged text which was published in the public edition of the plays in 1623, after Shakespeare's death. (Shakespeare 1) Shakespeare, in the area of tragedy as well as all other areas, is influenced by the playwrights who lived before, but swiftly surpassed them in time by adding his genius and personality to his plays.

Queen Elizabeth died without leaving heirs; King James IV of Scotland came to the British throne as King James I and this event has increased the interest of British people to the Scotland. It is believed that in order to protect his company and appeal to King James I, Shakespeare wrote the play Macbeth for him.

Samuel Taylor Coleridge and Andrew Cecil Bradley, famous theater critics of the period, highlighted the rapid development of the events in Macbeth rather than its shortness. Urgan argue that "the play is actually written longer, but due to be staged in the court, it is shortened by Shakespeare himself. The reason of this is the absence of the front lines giving rise to the action in the original play" (Urgan 6).

At the very beginning of the play, dizzying events go one after another. Immediately after Macbeth encountered with the witches, he learns that he is entitled with the title of Thane of Cawdor; on the same day, he invites the King Duncan to his palace; that very night, King Duncan is murdered and Macbeth is crowned as a king next morning.

Shakespeare's chief source for Macbeth was Holinshed's Chronicles (Macbeth), who based his account of Scotland's history (Mabillard). "Shakespeare has made changes as he wishes on this chronicle and in many cases; he digressed from the original history" (Urgan). Macbeth is also engaging work in terms of showing that how Shakespeare can successfully change the material he has. In Holinshed's Chronicles, it is obviously described how Scottish nobleman Donwald hosted the king Duffe, how he killed the King with the encouragement of his wife, how he put the blame on his drunk servants and then killed them without pity, how he beat himself up because of so-called pain when the murder came out. Shakespeare took this murder theme from Holinshed; but, he replaced Donwald with Macbeth and Duffe with Duncan. (Mabillard)

On the other hand, in the Chronicles, it is written that Banquo also involved to the conspiracy of homicide of King Duncan by Macbeth. However, Shakespeare has made some

changes on this issue, because he didn't want to imply that James I was convicted of treason to his ancestors. "Macbeth was specifically written as entertainment for the royal court, Shakespeare's inclusion of Macbeth's guilty conscience was a way in which he could both intrigue and compliment King James" (Mabillard).

Shakespeare's Macbeth is interpreted as the King Macbeth by the critics. In contrast, the King Macbeth ruled to Scotland with the integrity and honesty and established beneficial innovations in the first decade of his reign. However, the last years of his reign, he ruined all the good he did by showing a terrible persecution. On the other hand, Shakespeare's Macbeth is cruel and evil throughout his reign. Therefore, Shakespeare's Macbeth is more like Donwald.

II.II. THE POWER OF NATURE

The Nature was used in three ways in Shakespeare's plays:

In the first form, it is personified and it reacts like a human; sometimes, it is furious and it punishes people, and sometimes, it is kindhearted, it approves or endorses. In the second form of the Nature; it becomes an expression of man's inner world, it is the subconscious of a man and it is formed by the forces of his subconscious. In third form; it is a place which has direct effect on the sequence of events. For instance, it seen that the Nature is personified in the plays Macbeth, King Lear, The Winter's Tale and Julius Caesar. In King Lear and Macbeth, it is an expression of the inner world at the forefront as well as a place. Also, In Tempest, Othello, A Midsummer Night's Dream, As You Like It and Hamlet, it effects the play as a place in the same way.

In Macbeth, throughout the play, it is encountered with an angry nature except one scene. The sky roars and the gloom of darkness covers the entire series of events. In Act 2 Scene 4, the conversation between Old Man and Ross conveys the views of this mad nature. Ross says to Old Man:

Ha, good father,
 Thou seest the heavens, as troubled with man's act,
 Threatens his bloody stage. By th' clock 'tis day,
 And yet dark night strangles the travelling lamp.
 Is 't night's predominance or the day's shame
 That darkness does the face of Earth entomb
 When living light should kiss it? (Shakespeare)

Old Man completes what Ross said. When he is describing how an owl terribly shivered a hawk, Ross adds that Duncan's horses ate each other. After the death of Duncan, the Nature shows his anger with terrible reactions, and at the same time, it is like a prediction of what would happen in the future.

Throughout the play, the Nature looks tranquilly only in Act I Scene 6 in which Duncan and Banquo have a conversation. By the side of Macbeth's castle, Duncan is approaching his death and the serenity in the Nature is ironic. However, it reflects the reality of Duncan's inner world. Duncan is a benevolent king and in the last days of his reign he is in peace of having a son who is the potential heir of his throne. He trusts those around. The Nature is like accompanying Duncan's inner peace.

It is also depicted as a place: the play begins in the Duncan's palace and progresses toward Macbeth's castle. Macbeth's castle is alone in nature and it was built on a hill. The transition from Duncan's palace to the castle evokes a sense of transition from surrealism to realism in human. For instance, in the road between the palace and the castle, there are witches and they strengthen the surrealism of the castle.

II.III. THE SUPERNATURAL POWERS

In Macbeth, perhaps, the most significant play of Shakespeare in terms of supernatural characters, the role of witches is very important in the structural integrity of the play:

According to some critics, the play Macbeth has been renewed by other playwrights with various additions and extractions and the original text from Shakespeare's skillful hands is corrupted. Therefore, the parts about the witches are thought to belong to those playwrights. The witch scenes are reproached to Shakespeare, even, it is believed that those additions were made by Thomas Middleton. For those who lived in the era of Queen Elizabeth, supernatural being which is called a witch was literally true (Urgan).

Shakespeare did not give a place to supernatural beings in any of his play before. Considering that the witches might be thought as the main characters of the play, they play an important role in the development of the tragedy. If he murdered King Duncan without the prophecies by witches, this tragedy would not have the same effect. Shakespeare has brought a mysterious condition by adding witch characters and made the play way from mediocrity. "The witches, at the same time, are mysterious and incomprehensible characters, fate icons and evil debauchers, ugly and old freaks" (Honan).

Shakespeare's witches are complicated creatures and they reminiscent of the medieval thinking. Although, they resemble the witches as physical appearance, according to some critics, they are the messengers of the future, the representatives of evil and the beings revealed by the subconscious of Macbeth. These characters which are created by Shakespeare have been adopted as "witches" by the audience of era, because of their characteristics.

In Shakespeare's time, the word "weird" has been meant "fate", so, some critics have described the witches as the messengers of the future:

Wyrd is an Old English noun, a feminine one, from the verb weorthan "to become". It is related to the Old Saxon wurd, Old High German wurt, Old Norse urür. Wyrd is the ancestor of the more modern weird, which before it meant odd or unusual in the pejorative sense carried connotations of the supernatural, as in Shakespeare's weird sisters, the trio of witches in Macbeth. The original Wyrd Sisters were of course, the three Norns, the Norse Goddesses of destiny (Randolph).

The witches are the trigger of the dramatic actions in Macbeth. They have also a function in terms of fiction and stage management. They add a fantastic dimension to the play and strengthen the plastic sense of the stage. The witches play a main role in revelation of

Macbeth's subconscious. They are right there because Macbeth accommodates evil in his inner world. Actually, "Weird Sisters" do not make any prophecy. Whether the news that they inform Macbeth about is happened (they informs Macbeth after Thane of Cawdor is given to him) or likely to be happened.

Only Macbeth sees the ghost (the ghost of Banquo) in the play. Macbeth who is without borders in evil is not completely non-human creature because of his characteristics exhibited in advance. In this sense, the ghost is an expression of his internal contradictions, conflicts, so, it is a delusion.

III. CONCLUSION

In his all plays, the owners of the disruptive actions are human beings. Those who disrupt the harmony by killing the king are: Macbeth, Brutus and Cladius. Those who go as far as to jealousy and suspicion are: Othello and Leontes. Those who make matters worse while trying to be helpful are: Oberon, Puck and Lear. Those who disrupt the order by using unjust authority are: Frederick in *As You Like It* and Antonio in *The Tempest*.

While the order collapsed by the actions of the characters is re-establishing in the internal logic of the play, it cannot be reached a happy ending in none of the plays. It finds the true meaning of life in the possibility of this corruption. Therefore, the life consists of a chaos among temporary harmonies. And perhaps, these fleeting moments of harmony constitutes the meaning of life.

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